

Mannich Bases as Potential Polydentate Ligands : 2,5-Bis(benzylaminomethyl) Hydroquinone Complexes

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The chelating properties of the Mannich base, 2,5-bis(benzylaminomethyl) hydroquinone (BAH) have been described. The ligand has been obtained by condensing 1:4:2 of hydroquinone, formaldehyde and benzylamine in dioxan medium. The polymeric metal complexes, $[ML_2 \cdot 2H_2O]_n$, where M = Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II), L = $C_{22}H_{22}N_2O_2$, have been synthesized by refluxing the metal ion and the ligand in 1:1 ratio in a medium of DMF. The compounds are coloured powdery solids, insoluble in water and in common organic solvents. Analytical, magnetic and spectral studies indicate an octahedral geometry for the complexes. The ligand field parameters have been reported.

SCHIFF bases are known to have excellent chelating properties and their polydentate nature favours the formation of polymeric metal complexes. Though the formation of Mannich bases have been extensively investigated, no work appears to be on record on their complexes, inspite of the presence of favourable donors in suitable positions. An attempt has been made to investigate the behaviour of Mannich bases as potential polydentate ligands and this communication records the results obtained in this direction.

The Mannich base, 2,5-bis(benzylaminomethyl) hydroquinone (BAH)^{1,2} has been synthesized by the interaction of hydroquinone, formaldehyde and benzylamine. Structure of the compound shows that it is capable of behaving as a tetradentate ligand, the donor atoms being the phenolic oxygens and imino nitrogens (I).

I. 2,5-Bis(benzylaminomethyl)hydroquinone (BAH)

However, all the donors cannot coordinate to a single metal ion, since they are not favourably located. Each metal ion is coordinated through a phenolic oxygen and an imino nitrogen of the ligand. Two metal ions are thus attached to two ends of the ligand and the coordination number of metal ion permits the attachment of further ligand molecules, so that a chain polymeric structure is obtained (II).

Experimental

Materials: Hydroquinone (B.D.H.), benzylamine (E. Merck), formaldehyde (B.D.H.) and the metal salts (B.D.H.), $Co(CH_3COO)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, $Ni(CH_3COO)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ and $Cu(CH_3COO)_2 \cdot H_2O$ were employed. Dimethylformamide, dioxan and other solvents used were of reagent grade.

Elemental analyses: Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were determined by microanalytical methods. The metal contents of the complexes were estimated by chelometric titration, after decomposition of the complexes by fuming HNO_3 .

Infrared spectra: Infrared spectra of BAH and its complexes were recorded on Aculab 10 Beckman Infrared spectrophotometer in the range of $4000-600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ using KBr pellets.

Reflectance spectra: Diffuse spectra (uv/vis) in the solid state using MgO were recorded on VSU-2 spectrophotometer in the range 200-900 nm.

Magnetic measurements: The magnetic susceptibility measurements were done by Faraday's method at room temperature ($\sim 298^\circ K$).

Preparation of ligand: The compound was prepared by the method described by Burke, Hammer and Weatherbee^{1,2}: Formaldehyde (0.44 mol; 33 ml, 37% aqueous solution) was mixed with 50 ml of dioxan, cooled in ice, and benzylamine (24 ml; 0.22 mol) was added dropwise with constant stirring. To the above, hydroquinone (11.0 g; 0.10 mol) was added in small portions at a time, the mixture being stirred to ensure continuous dissolution of hydroquinone. The solution was refluxed at about 100° for 2 hr when a white coloured product separated. The mixture was cooled, the solid was filtered and recrystallised in methanol. The purified product was dried and was hydrolysed by dilute hydrochloric acid (20 ml) on a sand bath, when all the solid dissolved. The solution on keeping overnight yielded a white powdery solid. This was then dissolved in water and liquor ammonia was added to precipitate the base. The precipitate was washed with water till free from chloride (Yield 76%).

Synthesis of metal complexes: BAH (3.48 g) dissolved in DMF (50 ml), was gradually added to a DMF solution of the metal salt [2.42 g of $Co(CH_3COO)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, 2.49 g of $Ni(CH_3COO)_2$].

TABLE 1—COLOUR AND ANALYTICAL DATA

Compound	Colour	Elemental analyses % Found (Calcd.)			
		C	H	N	Metal
BAH(C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₂)	White	75.80 (75.86)	6.58 (6.89)	8.04 (8.10)	— —
Co(C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂).2H ₂ O	Reddish brown	58.20 (59.82)	5.02 (5.90)	6.38 (6.40)	13.28 (13.36)
Ni(C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂).2H ₂ O	Greyish green	58.20 (59.80)	5.00 (5.88)	6.35 (6.42)	13.26 (13.32)
Cu(C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂).2H ₂ O	Brown	58.05 (59.20)	4.97 (5.83)	6.28 (6.32)	24.00 (14.24)

TABLE 2—INFRARED SPECTRA OF BAH AND ITS COMPLEXES
(WAVE NUMBERS ARE IN CM⁻¹)

BAH	Co(II)	Ni(II)	Cu(II)	Assignment
3360	—	—	—	ν OH (phenolic)
—	3400	3400	3400	ν OH (H ₂ O)
3290	3040	3040	3060	ν NH
3260	2925	3020	2925	
1680	1650	1660	1650	δ NH
—	1630	1620	1600	δ H ₂ O
1320	1270	1270	1270	ν C-O

The magnetic moment values of the complexes show that all the three complexes are paramagnetic. From the magnetic moment values and reflectance spectra (Table 3) octahedral geometry is inferred. The various ligand field parameters which have been calculated, (Table 4) further confirm the geometry³⁻⁵.

The infrared spectrum of BAH (Table 2 ; wave numbers are in cm⁻¹) shows a band at 3360 which may be assigned to hydrogen bonded OH (phenolic) stretching frequency. A medium band at 3260 is

TABLE 3—MAGNETIC MOMENTS AND REFLECTANCE SPECTRA

Complex	Magnetic moment (B.M.) ^a	Positions of bands (cm ⁻¹)	Assignment	Geometry
Co(II)-BAH	5.02	10350	4 _{T 1g} → 4 _{T 2g} (F)	Octahedral
		21550 ^b	4 _{T 1g} → 4 _{A 2g} (F)	
		22220	4 _{T 1g} → 4 _{T 1g} (P)	
Ni(II)-BAH	3.14	10270	3 _{A 2g} → 3 _{T 2g} (F)	Octahedral
		15650	3 _{A 2g} → 3 _{T 1g} (F)	
		27220	3 _{A 2g} → 3 _{T 1g} (P)	
Cu(II)-BAH	1.98	10000	2 _{B 1g} → 2 _{A 1g}	Octahedral
		10869	2 _{B 1g} → 2 _{B 2g}	
		11363	2 _{B 1g} → 2 _{E g}	

a : B. M. = 9.273 × 10⁻²⁴ m², A

b : Calculated value.

4H₂O or 2.00 g of Cu(CH₃COO)₂.H₂O]. The mixture was refluxed over sand bath for 2-3 hr as necessary. The contents of the flask were cooled and the separated solid was filtered, washed successively with DMF and ether and dried over CaCl₂ under reduced pressure.

The compounds are all air stable coloured powders, insoluble in water as well as in ethanol, acetone, chloroform, benzene and nitrobenzene. The colour and analytical data of the complexes are presented in Table 1, ir spectral data in Table 2, magnetic characteristics and DRS in Table 3.

Results and Discussion

The general empirical formula : ML.2H₂O [where M=Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) ; L=C₂₂H₂₂N₂O₂] for the complexes is indicated from analytical data (Table 1).

due to -NH stretching frequency and the band at 1320 to C-O stretching frequency. The spectra of complexes do not have the band of the free ligand at 3360, which indicates the involvement of phenolic oxygen in complexation, with deprotonation of the phenolic hydrogen^{6,7}. The presence of a new strong band near 3400 in the complexes is due to OH stretching frequency of coordinated water.

TABLE 4—LIGAND FIELD PARAMETERS

Complex	10Dq (cm ⁻¹)	ν_2/ν_1	B' (cm ⁻¹)	β	β^0 (%)
Co(II)-BAH	11200	2.1	848	0.96	13.7
Ni(II)-BAH	10270	1.52	12960	0.81	11.2

10 Dq = Crystal field splitting energy

B' = Racah's parameter

β = Measure of covalency

β^0 = Percentage covalency

The OH deformation frequency at 1630 further shows the presence of H_2O^8 . The NH stretching frequency suffers a negative shift in the spectra of the complexes which indicates the coordination of nitrogen to the metal ion^{9,10}. The C-O stretching frequency which is observed at a lower wave number in the complexes, further confirms the coordination of phenolic oxygen¹¹ to the metal ion with the formation of C-O-M bond. The ir spectral data show that BAH acts as tetradentate chelating agent, coordinating through phenolic oxygens and imino nitrogens. All the four donors do not coordinate to the same metal ion due to steric factors, thus leading to the formation of polymeric¹²⁻¹⁴ chain of BAH-metal linkages (II).

II. Polymeric metal(II)-BAH complex, $[M.L.2H_2O]_n$.

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